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The Importance of English in the Era of Globalization for MI/SD Children

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Abstract

English is one of the languages of communication used all over the world. Up-to-date information in the fields of science, technology, politics, education, health, economics, and other fields is always written in foreign languages, especially English. In the era of globalization and free markets, all individuals must be able to compete for reliable resources. The role of English is so important that learning English should be an individual investment to achieve a bright life. But in reality, there are still many students, especially EFL learners, who have difficulty understanding English due to a lack of practice in daily life. Objectives: To help students understand the importance of learning English in the era of globalization and provide opportunities to participate in English language training.

Keywords ; Education, English, Globalization Era

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INTRODUCTION

English learning in schools is considered very important in the era of globalization and can be a development priority. Apart from the fact that English is an international language, mastering it opens up many good opportunities in various fields, including education. Therefore, to equip children with English language skills, it is a good idea to start the introduction of English from an early age. Recognizing the importance of the English language, many schools, especially at the elementary school level, increase the amount of time they spend teaching English to help students become more proficient in the language. In this modern era, English is an international language and an important language to learn. The influence of English is very important in this modern era because English is dominant in terms of communication and language is also the main means of communication. The importance of the role of English in various aspects of life, therefore it is very important for everyone in the world to understand and learn English. In an era where everyone competes with each other, competition for English proficiency is not only a means of self-development and intellectual improvement, but can also be an added value for individuals.

One of the factors is the status of English in Indonesia. In Indonesia itself, English is not the first and second language, but has the status of a foreign language. When students are at home, language is their native language. For example, Anto comes from Bangka Belitung, so the colloquial language used by Anto is Bangka. The same goes for schools from kindergarten to college level starting from onwards. The language used is Indonesian. This is because Indonesian is a language understood by the Indonesian state and must be used in all activities that are national and related to government affairs, as well as as a language of instruction for education. With 53 countries using English as their official language and ±400 million people speaking the language worldwide, learning English is the first step towards global communication.

In Indonesia, the use of foreign languages is increasingly prevalent and increasingly favored by schools and various international programs (Wijana, 2018). This phenomenon is very good, because it can help students master English in their school environment other than in certain courses or institutions. English training or thinning is very much in Indonesia. Various institutions offer their own advantages so that they can attract students to join the institution. But for those who have economic difficulties, the cost of training will be an obstacle for them to be able to hone their English skills at the course institution. However, in today's computerized time, learning English is not only

about following a course institution. There are various conveniences for them to be able to master English, namely downloading various portable learning applications on the Playstore or App store. (Aini & Riyantomo, 2019).

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative type of research. The selection of this method was carried out because the analysis could not be in the form of numbers and the researcher described all phenomena in society more clearly. In this study, the sampling technique used is purposive sampling, which is sampling based on certain objectives or considerations.

In addition to using qualitative research, this research also uses library research. Library research is a data collection technique by studying, studying, and understanding data sources in several books related to this research, called literature research because the data or materials needed to complete the research come from literature in the form of books, encyclopedias, dictionaries, journals, documents, magazines, and so on.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the era of globalization, cross-cultural communication is very important. English as the most commonly used international language in various fields, such as business, technology, science, and culture, allows people from different countries to communicate and share information more easily. English is important in today's era because the ability to speak English is a very important skill in the digital era. By having English proficiency, a person can communicate effectively globally, access a wider range of resources and information, and improve their abilities in various aspects of life, such as business, technology, and education.

In the era of globalization that we are experiencing today, technology continues to develop. With the development of technology, mastering English is the right place to face various modern challenges. Therefore, one of the goals of learning English is for students to be able to communicate both orally and in writing. This is to help you understand what is said and written in letters, articles, etc. when communicating in English. Or vice versa. When they want to communicate with their interlocutors, they do so smoothly and without difficulty. In other words, when students participate in communication situations, they learn to understand and be understood by their interlocutors. called him a competent language learner.

The importance of English language skills in social life in the era of globalization can be seen from various perspectives. From a communication perspective, English language skills have a very strategic role. The strategic role of English language skills is shown by the fact that English language skills are access to science and technology innovations and media for cross-cultural recognition and appreciation. The demand for the transfer of information and the transfer of science and technology from the source language (foreign language) makes English language skills and translation activities something important and necessary. From an economic perspective, English proficiency is an important activity because the world is increasingly united built on information sharing and communication sophistication. English language skills and translators will play an imperative role in the interaction between international companies and countries and governments. There are many cases of failure of business relationships due to misunderstandings and communication failures so that the ability to speak English is no longer solely a diversion of words but also involves the transformation of meaning and desire. For companies operating in various countries, English proficiency activities will be inevitable either to disseminate information or negotiate. From a political and cultural perspective, foreign language skills (English) and the profession of translators are also indispensable. Nowadays, international diplomacy is part of the external intestines of a country, including Indonesia. The success of an international exchange is highly dependent on English language skills and a successful translator. The ability to speak English for various works of art such as music, film and literature of a region is indispensable for the benefit of worldwide understanding of the region and its socio-cultural life. Thus, English language skills have become a medium of cultural exchange or cultural diplomacy.

English plays a very important role in the era of globalization for the following reasons:

1. **Universality:** English is a universal language and is widely spoken worldwide. Therefore, English language skills are very important in order to be able to communicate with people from different countries and cultures.
2. **Digital Impact:** Learning English in the digital era is also very important because technology has become an integral part of the learning process. Incorporating technology into English language learning improves content comprehension and engagement, as well as facilitating communication.
3. **The importance of civic education:** In the era of globalization, civic education is also very important. To form noble morals in society, civic education must be practiced in students' daily lives. Civic education must be context-specific, keep up with the times and always encourage students to actively face the era of globalization by mastering technology.
4. **The importance of Indonesian education:** Indonesian education is also very important. This is because Indonesian is the national language and functions as the language of science. Strategies to address challenges in Indonesian language teaching include a series of positive attitudes towards Indonesian, language development, language coaching, and language planning.
5. **Raising awareness:** It is also important to increase students' awareness of the importance of English language skills. For example, educational activities carried out directly at MI/SD AL – IT"TIHADYAH show that students' awareness of the importance of English language skills is increasing. Therefore, in the era of globalization, knowledge of English is very important to improve communication, improve skills, increase opportunities and form the noble morals of society.

In introducing English to children, it must be done with concrete or real activities, so that children are able to understand what is meant in the activities carried out. Examples of materials that can be introduced to children are one of them related to the ability of children to know English in simple and familiar materials with children, for example about colors, fruits, numbers and limbs. The following are the stages in learning English for children:

1. **Tuning in (Listening)** In addition to hearing us speak, children can also hear by reading storybooks in English, listening to simple songs or watching DVDs or videos in English. But for initial knowledge, as educators we must choose few and simple words.
2. **Talking** After children often hear in English, children can be encouraged to speak in simple sentences. For example, by implementing 30 minutes a day as family time to speak in English. Just like a toddler who has just started talking, the child also starts to speak in English even with one word like book when he sees his brother carrying a book. Then develop it into short sentences such as, she brings book.
3. **Perturning (Reading)** There are two common methods in teaching children to learn to read in English, namely entirety, dialect approach, and phonic.
 - a. The entire dialect approach is a method of learning to read by making language as one of the undivided units. This method emphasizes more on the meaning of a word.
 - b. Phonic is a method of learning to read through letters by spelling them one by one.
4. **Composing** This is a difficult stage in learning English, because there are many rules that must be followed. Usually Indonesians will definitely have difficulty speaking in English. Actually, it is not because they can't but because they are afraid of being wrong. Even if we mispronounce the arrangement of several sentences or the wrong words in the language, our interlocutor must understand. But it's different with writing, when we make a lot of grammatical and spelling mistakes, the person who reads our writing may not understand what we are writing. Because this is relatively difficult, writing is the last stage. As educators, we should not rush to teach linguistic use or writing if children have not mastered the previous three stages.

In MI/SD children, of course, introduction and learning from an early age should have been carried out, because that way the child will be more proficient in English. The role of parents here is very much needed because with the support of parents, the interest in learning English in MI/SD children will increase. The rapid development of this era requires all people to be able to do things that are increasingly developing, of course, also being able to speak English which should be the basic skill that every group has.

The role of parents, especially mothers, greatly determines their influence on the process of children's education in the home environment and ultimately on the success of children's learning at school. The role of the family is very large in the implementation of early childhood education. In this case, the active role of parents is very important. Parents need knowledge of English to buy books on the basics of English and teach them to children at home. The parenting that parents provide to their children is not temporary, short-term parenting, but parenting that represents direct interaction between parents and children. In parenting, they not only pass on facts, ideas, and knowledge, but also directly help maximize children's growth and development. In providing child care, parents should understand the needs of children according to their developmental age, not impose their own will.

CONCLUSION

The language that is very widely used throughout the country is English and is also the language used for international communication, one of which is in the field of education. The ability to speak English is currently very important to be able to support one's studies. For students, the advancement of technology and the current era of globalization require them to be proficient in English because English is one of the ways to face the future because this is related to the development of the times so there are so many challenges that they will get.

In the era of globalization, the importance of learning English for MI/SD children cannot be underestimated. English not only opens doors for international communication, access to information, and educational and career opportunities, but also contributes to the improvement of children's cognitive skills and cultural adaptation. Therefore, investing in learning English early is a strategic step to prepare the younger generation to face the challenges and take advantage of opportunities in this increasingly connected world. English language learning in MI/SD should be a priority in the educational curriculum to ensure children are ready for a global future full of international competition and collaboration.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Agustin, Yulia. (2011). The Position of English as a Language of Instruction in the World of Education. *Deiksis*, 3(4), 354-364.
- Dalilah, Wafa Khilda, and Mega Febriani Sya. "Problems of Speaking English in Elementary School Children." *Karimah Tauhid* 1.4 (2022): 474-480.
- Diniyah, Faqihatud. "Parents' and teachers' perceptions of English in early childhood at Aba Karangmalang Kindergarten, Yogyakarta." *Tarbiyah: Scientific Journal of Education* 6.2 (2017).
- Nuraeni, S. Pd. "English in the Era of Globalization." *Theory & Innovation of Future Education* 18 (2021).
- Putranti, Bernadetta Eko, and Suprih Ambawani. "The importance of learning English for elementary school age children in the neighborhood of rt 37 rw 13 Giwangan Village, Umbulharjo District." *Dharma Bakti* (2019): 177-183.
- Riani, Desmy, et al. "Socialization and Education on the Importance of Learning English in the Era of Globalization for MTS Fitra Mulia Students in Nambo Village." *INTEGRITY: Journal of Community Service* 7.1 (2023): 100-110.
- Sari, Nasywa Nur Kamila, Zahra Pinkan Maulida, and Aulia Salmawati. "The Importance of English in the Era of Globalization." *Karimah Tauhid* 3.3 (2024): 3685-3692.